

Studies on Vanadium-Thiophene-2-Hydroxamic Acid Complexes. A 1:3 Metal-Ligand System.

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Spectrophotometric method has been utilized for the evaluation of stepwise formation constants of a 1:3 metal-ligand system. Photometric data by solvent extraction technique were utilized for the determination of composition and calculation of the said constants for vanadium-thiophene-2-hydroxamic acid complex at 590 nm (λ_{\max}). Both Yatsimirskii's and Leden's graphical extrapolation methods were applied with necessary modification to calculate their values of stepwise stability constants. The ligand association constant for the complex was determined by solving a fourth-degree equation with the help of a computer. The product of the two stepwise stability constants agreed fairly well with the overall formation constant calculated by Leden's method. The $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ for the system are found to be 4.99 and 4.83 by Yatsimirskii's method and those by Leden's method are 5.09 and 4.59 respectively. The ligand association constant value, $\log K_3$ is 5.57 at 25°.

THIOPHENE-2-hydroxamic acid like other hydroxamic acids¹ forms complexes with vanadium(V). The violet complex of vanadium extracted in chloroform at pH 3.5 and having maximum absorption at 590nm has been utilized² for determination of low concentration (0.05-1.5%) of vanadium in various materials. In the present paper the authors have selected the bidentate chelating agent for study of the complex equilibria in solution since the metal chelate enables the determination of stability constants data for 1:3 metal-ligand system which are very few in literature³. This has also facilitated the development of a spectrophotometric technique for evaluating accurately the stepwise formation constants of complexes with a high metal-ligand ratio. A new approach for evaluation of the constants in solution by two dimensional graphical extrapolation methods has been suggested by an extension of Yatsimirskii's method⁴ and that of Leden⁵ from "solubility method" to spectrophotometric technique.

Experimental

Standard vanadium solution was prepared by dissolving ammonium vanadate (Riedel-de Haen A.G.) in ammonia and then diluted to known volume by distilled water. The vanadium content of this solution was determined by complexometric titration with EDTA(Na-salt). A standard solution (1×10^{-4} moles/litre) was prepared by appropriate dilution of the stock solution containing 1.0 mg/ml vanadium.

Reagent was prepared by the reported method². Standard reagent solutions of desired strength in alcohol free chloroform were used and stored in amber coloured bottle. A standard 0.2N solution of potassium chloride was used to maintain the ionic strength constant in a total volume of 25 ml. Chemicals used were all analR grade.

Apparatus :

A Unicam SP-600 spectrophotometer with glass absorption cells of 1.00 cm light path were used for all photometric measurements. A Cambridge pH-meter

(Model Bench type) with a glass-calomel electrode system was employed for pH adjustment. Measurements were made at 25°.

Composition of the complex :

A solvent extraction procedure using chloroform as solvent was followed with equimolar solutions of vanadium and reagent and utilized to find out the molar composition of the complex. The photometric measurements by Job's method of continuous variation and mole-ratio method made at 590 nm and pH 3.5 have indicated a metal to ligand ratio of 1:3.

Procedure :

A suitable aliquot of vanadium(V) solution (1×10^{-4} moles/litre) was adjusted to pH 3.5 and transferred quantitatively to a 100 ml separatory funnel. To it was added varying amounts of the reagent solutions in chloroform. The mixture was then shaken for 5 min. and the violet coloured chloroform layer was allowed to settle and drained out in a 50 ml beaker containing little anhydrous sodium sulphate. The aqueous phase after extraction was washed with a further 5 ml portions of chloroform. The combined extract was diluted to 25 ml with chloroform. The absorbances were measured at the wavelength maxima 590 nm against solvent blank.

Results and Discussion :

Determination of Stepwise stability Constants : Yatsimirskii's method :

To calculate the three stepwise formation constants we modified an extrapolation method developed by Yatsimirskii⁴. From the series of determinations of the absorbance of solutions containing the complex species, we obtained a series of values and thus the mean molar absorptivity according to the formula :

$$e = \frac{A}{(C_m) \cdot l}$$

where e is the mean molar absorptivity ; A , the absorbance of the solution containing metal complexes ; C_m , the total metal concentrations and l , the thickness of the absorbance cell (1 cm in the present case).

The ligand, L, thiophene-2-hydroxamic acid reacted with the metal, M, vanadium(V) to form complexes $ML_1, ML_2, ML_3 \dots \dots ML_n$ having the respective formation constants, $K_1, K_2, K_3 \dots \dots K_n$. We assumed, at the concentration employed, that only species ML_1, ML_2 , and ML_3 were present and the absorbance of the solution could be expressed as

$$A = e_0[M] + e_1[ML_1] + e_2[ML_2] + e_3[ML_3] + e_L[L] \dots 1$$

The bracketed term represent the equilibrium concentrations of the enclosed species while e values are their respective molar absorptivity.

From the Relationship :

$$C_M = [M] + [ML_1] + [ML_2] + [ML_3] \dots (2)$$

and the value for e and the equation (1)

$$e = \frac{e_1 K_1 [L] + e_2 K_1 K_2 [L]^2 + e_3 K_1 K_2 K_3 [L]^3}{1 + K_1 [L] + K_1 K_2 [L]^2 + K_1 K_2 K_3 [L]^3} \dots (3)$$

The co efficient of the equation for e (Eqn.3), were searched by constructing a series of subsidiary functions and extrapolating them to the zero value of the variable. The different subsidiary functions are defined as follows :

$$\text{Lim } f_1 = \text{Lim } \frac{e}{[L]} = a_1 = 8.9 \times 10^9 \quad (\text{Fig. 1})$$

$$[L] \rightarrow 0 \quad [L] \rightarrow 0$$

$$\text{Lim } f_2 = \text{Lim } \frac{f_1 - a_1}{[L]} = a_2 = (-) 11.1 \times 10^{14} \quad (\text{Fig. 1})$$

$$[L] \rightarrow 0 \quad [L] \rightarrow 0$$

$$\text{Lim } f_3 = \text{Lim } \frac{f_2 - a_2}{L} = a_3 = 6.8 \times 10^{19} \quad (\text{Fig. 1})$$

$$[L] \rightarrow 0 \quad [L] \rightarrow 0$$

and introducing $Y (= \frac{1}{[L]})$

Fig 1. Subsidiary functions f_1, f_2 and f_3 as a function of the free-ligand concentration L

Fig. 2. Molar extinction co-efficient e as a function of the reciprocal of free-ligand concentration L. Subsidiary functions g and g_1 as a reciprocal of free-ligand concentration L.

$$\lim_{Y \rightarrow 0} e = b_1 = 6.25 \times 10^4 \quad (\text{Fig. 2})$$

$$\lim_{Y \rightarrow 0} g = \lim_{Y \rightarrow 0} \frac{e - b_1}{Y} = b_2 = (-) 0.267 \quad (\text{Fig. 2})$$

$$\lim_{Y \rightarrow 0} g_1 = \lim_{Y \rightarrow 0} \frac{e - b_2}{Y} = b_3 = 1.905 \quad (\text{Fig. 2})$$

Since we had determined the absorbances for a series of solutions of known concentration of ligand, then with equation (1) a value of e was computed for known values of $[L]$. Yatsimirskii constructed the subsidiary functions, f_2 etc. by differentiation of the function j_1 and extrapolation of the derivative to zero ligand concentration and so on. The values of the coefficients of equation for e was obtained by graphical extrapolation method. In this paper, authors constructed the said functions gradually with graphical extrapolation of the functions, and the values of the coefficients were calculated by solution of a polynomial with computer programming.

The relations of the stepwise stability constants (i. e. K_1, K_2 and K_3) with a_1, a_2, a_3 and b_1, b_2, b_3 are given by the following equations :

$$a_1 = e_1 K_1 \quad b_1 = e_3$$

$$a_2 = e_2 K_1 K_2 - e_1 K_1^2 \quad \text{and} \quad b_2 = \frac{e_2 - e_3}{K_3}$$

$$a_3 = e_3 K_1 K_2 K_3 - e_1 K_1^3 \quad b_3 = \frac{e_1 - e_2}{K_2}$$

The above equations were solved to have one fourth degree equation in K_2 . The solution of the polynomial in K_2 was obtained by Fortran programming on a scientific computer CDC 3600. The Newton-Raphson's method was chosen to have the initial guess value of K_2 . Results are given in Tables 1 and 3. *Leden's Method* :

In order to calculate the successive stability constants of a sparingly soluble complex Leden⁵, Fronaeus⁶ and others^{7,8} used the function φ , which is the ratio of the over-all concentration of metal C_M to the equilibrium concentration of free-metal ions in the reaction :

$$M + nL \rightleftharpoons ML_n$$

$$\varphi = \frac{C_M}{[M]}$$

Since the over all concentration of metal in solution (C_M) is the sum of the concentrations of complexes of the type ML_n , it follows that

$$\varphi = 1 + \beta_1 [L] + \beta_2 [L]^2 + \beta_3 [L]^3 + \dots + \beta_n [L]^n$$

If the degree of complex formation is known, then the successive stability constants may be calculated by Leden's method. In this case the degree of complex formation, φ , was evaluated from the absorption data of the complex, in modification of Leden's solubility data. The value of function Ψ_1 is found from the equation

$$\Psi_1 = \frac{\varphi - 1}{[L]} = \beta_1 + \beta_2 [L] + \beta_3 [L]^2$$

The function Ψ_1 is reduced to β_1 when $[L]=0$. The constant β_1 or K_1 was found by graphical extrapolation of the function Ψ_1 as the intercept on the ordinate. Fig. 3 shows that the value is 1.24×10^5 . The function Ψ_2 may then be found by means of the equation

$$\Psi_2 = \frac{\Psi_1 - \beta_1}{[L]}$$

and, $\lim_{[L] \rightarrow 0} \Psi_2 = \beta_2 = K_1 K_2$

Fig. 3. Subsidiary functions Ψ_1, Ψ_2 as a function of the free-ligand concentration.

This is illustrated in Fig. 3 where the intercept gave $\beta_2 = 4.8 \times 10^9$. Table 3 shows that $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values obtained by modified Yatsimirskii's and Leden's method respectively are in agreement and that $\log K_3 > \log K_2$. Hydroxamic acids (RH_2) form complexes with vanadium(V) which can be isolated in the solid state as $VO(OH)(RH)_2$ ⁹ where the two hydrogen atoms of RH_2 are present in the hydroxamide

From the stability data it appears to us that the two of the ligand molecules are bonded to the metal ion differently than the third unit. Probably the two ligand molecules are bidentate and the third one is associated with the complex as hydrogen bonded to the oxygen atom as $VO(OH)(RH)_2(RH_2)$. This third unit then may be in resonance with the other two in such a way

that always two ligand molecules are attached to the vanadium atom as bidentate ligand molecules and the third one associated through the oxygen atom. If this assumption is valid, this will then account for the higher

values of $\log K_3$ as obtained by Yatsimirskii's method. The last step in 1:3 metal complex formation may be regarded as only association of a ligand molecule.

TABLE 1—VANADIUM (V)-(THIOPHENE-2-HYDROXAMIC ACID)
Metal = Reagent = $1 \times 10^{-4} M$; Metal:Ligand = 1:3; pH = 3.5; solvent = Chloroform
Time for Extraction = 5 min; Metal taken = 4 ml of $1 \times 10^{-5} M$; Final volume = 25 ml. Absorbance for metal conc. $1.6 \times 10^{-5} M/lit. = 1.05$; $\lambda_{max} = 590 \text{ nm}$.

Solution	Total ligand conc., M/lit. ($C_L \times 10^5$)	Absorbance	Free-ligand conc., M/lit. ($[L] \times 10^5$)	Molar Extinction ϵ ($\times 10^{-4}$)	f_1 ($\times 10^{-9}$)	f_2 ($\times 10^{-14}$)	f_3 ($\times 10^{-19}$)	g ($\times 10^{-5}$)	g_1 ($\times 10^2$)	g_1 ($\times 10^1$)
1	0.8	0.143	0.1463	0.8937	6.167	—	—	6.831	-0.7839	0.1308
2	1.2	0.221	0.1899	1.381	7.274	-8.561	13.37	5.265	-0.9247	0.2623
3	1.6	0.271	0.3610	1.693	4.691	—	6.844	2.770	-1.682	0.6115
4	2.0	0.350	0.4001	2.188	5.468	-8.58	6.299	2.500	-1.625	0.8754
5	2.4	0.403	0.5577	2.519	4.516	-7.863	5.805	1.793	-2.081	1.405
6	2.8	0.500	0.5133	3.125	6.088	—	—	1.948	-1.604	1.604
7	3.2	0.550	0.6857	3.438	5.014	—	—	1.458	-1.928	2.357
8	4.0	0.650	1.0288	4.062	3.949	-4.811	6.112	0.9718	-2.251	4.180
9	4.8	0.764	1.308	4.775	3.652	-4.014	5.419	0.7647	-1.929	6.244
10	5.6	0.835	1.781	5.219	2.930	-3.352	4.349	0.5614	-1.837	9.296
11	6.4	0.843	2.548	5.269	2.067	-2.681	3.304	0.3924	-2.500	13.43

- - - Not plotted for wide deviations.

TABLE 2—VANADIUM (V) - (Thiophene-2-hydroxamic Acid)

Metal = Reagent = $1 \times 10^{-4} M$; Metal:Ligand = 1:3

pH = 3.5; Solvent = chloroform

Time for Extraction = 5 min

Metal taken = 4 ml of $1 \times 10^{-4} M$; Final volume = 25 ml.

Total metal conc. = $9.0 \times 10^{-5} M (= CM)$

Absorbance for metal conc. $1.6 \times 10^5 M = 1.05$; $\lambda_{max} = 590 \text{ nm}$

Solution	Total ligand conc., M/lit. ($C_L \times 10^5$)	Absorbance	Conc. of metal complexed M/lit. ($\times 10^5$)	Equilb. ligand conc., M/lit. ($[L] \times 10^5$)	Equilb. Metal conc., M/lit. ($[M] \times 10^5$)	Degree of complex formation, $\frac{-CM}{M}$	Ψ_1 ($\times 10^{-5}$)	Ψ_2 ($\times 10^{-9}$)
1	2.8	0.500	0.7619	0.5133	0.8381	1.909	1.771	10.34
2	3.2	0.550	0.8381	0.6857	0.7619	2.100	1.603	5.294
3	4.0	0.650	0.9904	1.028	0.6096	2.625	1.580	3.305
4	4.8	0.764	1.164	1.308	0.4360	3.669	2.041	6.125
5	5.6	0.835	1.273	1.781	0.3270	4.894	28.186	5.311
6	6.4	0.843	1.284	2.548	0.3160	5.063	1.594	1.390

TABLE 3—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS FOR VANADIUM COMPLEX (METAL:LIGAND = 1:3) AT 25°

Method	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log K_3$	$\log K$
Yatsimirskii's	4.99	4.83	5.57	15.39
Leden's	5.09	4.59	—	—

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